

Analysis of Academic Engagement in Technical Education Students: multiple case studies

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Abstract

Student academic engagement is a key indicator of educational success, especially in technical contexts. The objective of this study was to analyze the factors that impact the academic engagement of technical education students in a public educational institution, through the case study of three different sections. The study was developed from a qualitative-descriptive perspective and non-experimental design, in which non-participant observation and structured interviews were used with three sections of students in a technical program. The data from the study were organized into central categories that allowed the identification of behaviors involved with academic engagement and the underlying causes. The findings evidenced that a close relationship with the teacher and clarity in instructions encourage active participation, mainly in high-achieving students. On the other hand, in low-achieving students, lack of intrinsic motivation, limited social support, and negative perceptions of the physical classroom environment were identified as significantly reducing their academic engagement. These differences highlight the need to adapt pedagogical strategies to the specific characteristics of each group. This analysis of engagement emphasizes the need to design innovative pedagogical strategies such as practicum and collaborative work to foster academic engagement aligned with students' enlightened interests and expectations. The research provides integrative views of threats and opportunities to further both the educational experience in technical settings and the expectations of the students involved.

Key words: Case study, Academic engagement, Education, Learning strategy, Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Problematic Reality

Academic Engagement is understood as a meta-construct that can be analyzed from different theoretical points of view, and particularly associated with the study of dropout and retention, it allows to address this problem under a preventive/positive perspective that, on the other hand, gives the possibility to address the phenomenon of student retention with due attention [1]. However, despite the importance of academic commitment in the educational field, it is confronted with various problems that hinder the achievement of the expected results.

According to Sihombing et al. [2], academic commitment is a dependent variable of factors such as leadership and trust in educational institutions, which in turn are determinants of performance; thus, they note that in contexts where there is institutional limitation, in the sense of scarcity of resources or disinterest in professional development, there is a disconnection between academic commitment and expected performance. Likewise, modalities such as online education without adequate preparation have led to their deterioration and, therefore, students have not become fully committed to their academic activities [3]. Academic engagement in Latin America is presented as a variable of considerable importance in education, due to its importance in curbing school dropout and ensuring the educational path. According to Bravo et al. [4], academic engagement is a multidimensional phenomenon that includes affective, behavioral and cognitive aspects that operate together to determine a quality educational experience of its participants.

In the context of inclusive education, academic engagement is a crucial factor influencing students' access to and retention in education systems. According to a UNESCO education monitoring report, many barriers such as discrimination, stereotyping and alienation prevent learners from feeling valued and respected, which affects their sense of belonging and ultimately their engagement in education. These barriers result in exclusion that can lead to poor academic performance and school dropout, perpetuating social and economic inequalities [5].

In Peru, according to a report by the National Institute of Statistics and Informatics, in the year 2021, the gross school attendance rate corresponding to the population between 12 and 16 years of age reached the value of 94.2% and the net rate reached a value of 83.5% [6]. In Peru, academic engagement has great significance as a predictor of success in the educational trajectory of a university student. Martínez et al [7] consider that this multidimensional construct is influenced by psychological, personal and academic variables. The most significant determinants are satisfaction with the chosen career, personal flourishing and academic self-efficacy. On the other hand, The proportion of secondary education students aged 17-18 years completing secondary education is lower compared to enrollment and attendance data for the same age group, although there was an increase from 72.9% in 2017 to 76.8% in 2019 [8].

Thus, the need arises to develop an understanding of academic commitment in secondary technical education students, an area that is normally little researched in the Peruvian or Latin American context, despite the advances that may have been made in terms of identifying variables associated with the existence of academic commitment at higher levels of education, where variables such as personal satisfaction or academic self-efficacy do exist, but there is a void of not knowing how they can shape academic commitment in technical secondary school students or, in their effect, how the dynamics of each of the training sections can be further defined by academic commitment in students.

B. Literature Review

1) Academic Engagement

Academic engagement has been approached by different authors who attempt to define it in many ways [9], [10]. With respect to the different views of each, they all seem to agree that it is an active and meaningful participation in various educational processes. In this regard, Kahu [11] offers an interesting comprehensive view of engagement by exploring the behavioral, psychological, and sociocultural dimensions of it as a process of co-creation. In addition, the author describes this concept with many more characteristics for a better understanding.

The author mentions in an academic setting, engagement manifests itself, first, as proactive participation, which is defined as interactive; this arises from the psychological response to constant interaction with a particular learning object or activity. Second, it means that learner engagement is not fixed, but that active engagement changes through a series of stages within a framework and context of engagement, which is both enabling and constraining to the individual's growth. Moreover, engagement is not an act that takes place in isolation; it is a social practice that develops within the network of social relationships and interactions. Such relationships, or linkages, extend beyond the boundaries of the classroom because they are affected by broader situational parameters such as curriculum, institutional policies, and relationships within the learner's environment.

Academic engagement is an existential state, that is, a psychological state that is defined by energy, effort and exertion in school work and activities (vigor), enthusiasm and identification with academic work, pursuit of academic projects (dedication), and full concentration based on exploring and enjoying the academic activities themselves (absorption). It indicates not only the student's involvement in learning but also the student's emotional and motivational relationship with the educational environment [12]. At a conceptual level, it is considered by educators and researchers as a result of a successful combination of positive psychology and study orientation, agreeing that aspects such as vigor, dedication, and absorption are considered [13]. Based on this, it can be said that it is a positive construct with respect to learning, which explains the difficulties in relation to motivation, school dropout and performance in order to achieve academic success [14].

2) Academic commitment formation process

According to Rigo and Rovere [15], commitment is constructed and reconstructed, regardless of what these implications suggest about the students, their identity, the value and meaning that each one gives to their experiences and interactions. The authors emphasize that commitment is not a fixed concept, but is continually being shaped by the perceptions and identities of the students. That is, the meaning given to engagement may vary depending on the context of each student's lived experience, just as it may depend on the value that each student places on those same interactions in the classroom context.

3) Categories of academic commitment

Reeve et al. [16] mention two categories of engagement, reactive and proactive. The reactive category occurs when the student is involved in the tasks that teachers have prepared for learning, emotionally, behaviorally and cognitively; but the commitment does not only concern the fact of receiving indications, but the students expose the proactivity of making

comments, suggestions, asking questions that help them to progress during the teaching-learning process. The proactive actions of the student allow him or her to influence the dynamics of the class, which produces an increase in performance and personal motivation, thus improving the general conditions of the learning process. For Bandura [17], a person can be active in his or her learning if there is recognition in the context he or she is performing and a sense of self-efficacy. This faith in his capabilities gives him the power to have control of his own self-regulation and of the situation that occurs in the environment where it is taking place.

4) *Factors affecting commitment*

Different studies talk about some factors that have an impact on academic engagement, such as personal background, family and socioeconomic status. As, for example, with respect to the impact that education has on students' civic engagement, it has been pointed out that students whose parents are professionals or have significant work experience have stronger civic engagement [18].

In this sense, motivation is considered one of the primary elements that influence academic engagement and is subdivided into two categories, which are intrinsic and extrinsic. In self-determination theory, motivation is defined as a form of internal or external drive that can stimulate a student to engage in an activity [19]. On the other hand, intrinsic motivation is related to personal satisfaction and the desire to excel, while extrinsic motivation is generated by obtaining rewards such as good grades or social recognition. Likewise, the study by García et al. [20] highlights that the use of gamification strategies increases academic motivation by adding game aspects to the teaching processes that increase student autonomy and participation. According to Pintrich [21], motivation also has an impact on learning strategies and, as a consequence, on academic performance.

Moreover, nowadays, the use of technologies in education has changed the way in which students interact with academic content. Thus, the use of gamified platforms, such as Classcraft, has generated an improvement in student motivation and engagement [20]. These tools make it possible to personalize learning, monitoring academic progress and peer-to-peer collaboration, therefore, they can significantly increase the active participation of students during the educational process [22].

C. *Justification*

The research work develops its study in a public educational institution in Lima focusing on three sections. This approach has the virtue of identifying the factors that determine academic commitment in an educational space characterized by diversity and diverse socioeconomic realities, in such a way that it provides an integral vision of the interaction of the faces of the phenomenon of public technical education.

D. *Objectives*

In this context, the general objective is to analyze the factors that have an impact on the academic commitment of technical education students in a public educational institution in Lima, through a case study of three different sections. In addition, the specific objectives are as follows:

- Characterize the proactive and reactive category of academic engagement in technical education students.
- To identify differences in academic commitment among students with high, medium and low academic performance, in order to identify patterns, differences and opportunities for improvement in their academic performance.
- To propose strategies that foster academic engagement in students considering the factors analyzed.

Likewise, it is intended to answer the following research questions:

- ¿What are the characteristics of the proactive and reactive categories of academic engagement in technical education students?
- ¿What differences exist in academic engagement among students with high, medium and low academic performance?
- ¿What pedagogical strategies can be implemented to foster academic engagement in students, considering the factors that affect their participation and performance?

II. METHODOLOGY

A. *Method*

The study was of a basic type because its main purpose is to generate knowledge and theoretical understanding of academic engagement in technical education students [23]. The approach was qualitative, since what was proposed was, to understand in

depth, the factors that determine the academic commitment of students in technical education, therefore, it was convenient for the exploration of the particular experiences, the ways of perceiving them and the students' own dynamics in the field of a public education [24]. In addition, it was descriptive, since it focused on characterizing and detailing the factors that influence academic engagement, highlighting the particularities of the proactive and reactive categories in students [25].

The research design was non-experimental, as it is a multiple case study, since three different sections of a public educational institution in Lima will be analyzed in depth. The multiple case design allows exploring the particularities of each case individually, as well as identifying patterns and differences among them, providing a comprehensive and comparative view on the factors that influence students' academic engagement [26]. In addition, the study has a cross-sectional cut since the information will be collected at a single point in time. According to Manterola et al. [27], from a temporal and spatial point of view cross-sectional studies are observational and descriptive, measurements are carried out on a single occasion.

On the other hand, it was considered necessary to determine a procedure in order to obtain a higher level of credibility and consistency in the study, in addition to the value provided by other strategies applied such as the careful selection of the interviewees and the analysis of information. Thus, Figure 1 shows a flow chart of the research procedure, which covers the selection of the sample, including the design of the instrument, validation by means of expert judgment and ending with the establishment of conclusions.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the research process

B. Participants

The study population is composed of fifth year high school students from a public educational institution that attends technical education programs in Peru. A sample was selected from 3 different sections, including sections A, B and F, from each of which 10 students were selected, the ages of the students ranged between 16 and 17 years old. The type of sampling used was non-probabilistic by convenience, since they were selected taking into account that the study of 3 different cases was required:

- Section A (high academic performance): Comprised of students with grade point averages between 16 and 20, characterized by being active in class, high level of commitment to homework and regular attendance.
- Section B (medium performance): Consisting of students with grade point averages between 11 and 15, who show variability in their performance and an intermediate level of commitment to school activities.
- Section F (low academic performance): In which there are students whose grade point average was between 6 and 10, identified by recurrent academic difficulties, low participation in class and a higher rate of absences and tardiness.

These sections were selected for the purpose of assessing academic engagement in cohorts of different performance levels to allow for a deeper analysis of the factors affecting their participation and motivation. This approach follows the logic of contrast case sampling that helps to uncover different patterns within an examined phenomenon [28].

TABLE I
SAMPLE DETAIL

Section	Performance	Rating	Quantity	Female	Male	Coding
A	High	16-20	10	4	6	A1-A10
B	Medium	11-15	10	6	4	B1-B10
F	Low	6-10	10	4	6	F1-F10

C. *Research techniques*

Semi-structured interviews are used as a technique to investigate the perception, attitude and action of students regarding their academic commitment. Defined as a technique that combines open and closed questions to explore in depth the perceptions, attitudes and behaviors of the participants on a specific topic [29]. Likewise, the instrument used will be a semi-structured interview guide, which contains 8 questions, based on the proactive and reactive categories of academic engagement, Table 2 shows their subcategories. This instrument is a document whose purpose is to collect important information for a research, it can be done manually or computerized [25].

TABLE II
CATEGORIES AND SUBCATEGORIES OF ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT

Categorical variable	Category	Sub Category
Academic commitment	Proactive	Relationship with the teacher
		Intrinsic motivation
		Interest in the subject
		Social support in the classroom
	Reactive	Clarity of instructions
		Difficulty of tasks
		Physical environment of the classroom
		Academic load and time

On the other hand, non-participant observation was also used as a technique, understood as a methodology that allows systematically obtaining records of the behaviors and dynamics of people in a given situation, observing them without the observer participating in the observed activities [24]. This technique was oriented to identify classroom dynamics linked to academic engagement. The technique's instrument was a structured observation guide, which made it possible to record the behavior and dynamics that students put into practice in the classroom in a systematic approach, paying special attention to the two categories of academic engagement: proactive and reactive.

D. *Procedure*

The sources from which the information was extracted in this study were the interviews and the observation of the dynamics of each section. Regarding the interviews, these were conducted and recorded using Google Meet, the answers were later transcribed and organized in Microsoft Excel and in Lucidchart organizers, to facilitate the analysis of the answers given by the students.

At the same time, non-participant observation was conducted in the classroom to capture data related to students' academic engagement. These observations were stored in an analysis matrix in Excel to allow the identification of patterns of participation and interaction during the lessons in the sections that made up the sample.

In the present work, informed consent and voluntary participation of the research subjects was guaranteed, prioritizing basic aspects such as confidentiality and anonymity, and making use of an adequate treatment of the data. Data that were identifiable in relation to the subjects were treated only for the purpose of this research and once the study was completed they were destroyed. Both the interviews and the observations were conducted in a climate of respect and ensuring that the subjects did not feel uncomfortable. The results achieved were exposed to be transparent and truthful and the subjects were given the opportunity to know the final results, together with the fact of thanking them for their collaboration in the development of the work.

E. Information analysis

In order to meet the objectives of the study, the data analysis strategy used by Flick [30], which is oriented to the optimization of large amounts of information or their complexity, was used as a reference. This procedure involves the codification of information and data reduction and transformation operations to obtain reliable results and make it possible to draw conclusions.

Likewise, for the thematic analysis of the semi-structured interview, Clarke and Braun [31] were taken into account, beginning with a slow reading of the transcription of the responses, the units of analysis were identified and the information was organized according to the categories and subcategories established in Table 2. Thus, syntheses were established for each of the questions asked, from which those factors that impact academic commitment were determined.

The analysis of the information obtained through the observation guide was carried out using a qualitative coding strategy, allowing the identification of recurrent patterns in the students' behavior in relation to academic engagement. First, the data will be organized according to the proactive and reactive categories and the corresponding subcategories. Subsequently, a thematic analysis process was applied, where similarities and differences between students' academic performance levels will be identified, evaluating their degree of involvement in the classroom. Through this systematization, it is expected to interpret the factors that limit academic engagement, allowing the formulation of pedagogical strategies that respond to the specific needs of each study group.

III. RESULTADOS

This research presents an analysis of the responses of three groups of students with different academic performance levels (high, average, and low) and how the different categories of proactive and reactive academic engagement are reflected in each of them. Through semi-structured interviews and systematic observations, patterns of behavior and perceptions were identified that reveal the determining factors of engagement in each group.

A. Proactive Category

Relationship with the teacher

How do you describe your relationship with the teacher and how does it influence your participation in class?

- Section A:
A1: "My teacher always supports me when I have questions, that motivates me to learn more and want to participate in class."
- Section B:
B3: "My relationship with the teacher is normal, but I don't talk to him much."
- Section F:
F8: "I don't feel close to my teachers, nor do I trust any of them, I don't feel it matters whether I participate or not."

Intrinsic motivation

What motivates you to actively participate in class activities?

- Section A:
A2: "I am motivated to learn because I see that each topic covered in class is important for my higher education."
- Section B:
B3: "I participate when a topic of interest to me is discussed in class, but not always."
- Section F:
F6: "Actually, what would motivate me to participate in class is if I would get extra points, otherwise I wouldn't do it."

Interest in the topic

How important is it that the topics studied are related to your interests or goals?

- Section A:
A2: "The topics that interest me are those that help me enhance my knowledge for the technical career I want to pursue."
- Section B:
B2: "Some topics interest me, but others don't."
- Section F:
F4: "I don't see any use in the topics we study, so I don't consider them important."

Social support in the classroom

What impact do your classmates have on your interest and participation in class?

- Section A:

A3: "My classmates always help me when I don't understand something and that motivates me to want to learn more and participate in classroom activities."

- Section B:

B6: "I feel like my classmates only support me when it comes to group work; other than that, everyone looks out for themselves in class activities."

- Section F:

F7: "I don't usually work with my colleagues; everyone does their own thing."

B. Reactive Category

Clarity of instructions

Are the task instructions clear and how do they affect your performance?

- Section A:

A4: "In most cases I understand what I should do; if not, the teacher explains it to me."

- Section B:

B9: "The instructions are clear, however, sometimes I don't understand what to do, but I'm embarrassed to ask."

- Section F:

F5: "Sometimes I don't understand the instructions and I prefer not to pay attention to the class anymore."

Difficulty of tasks

How do you approach difficult tasks and what aspects help or hinder you?

- Section A:

A7: "Even if they are difficult, I always try to solve them and ask for help if necessary."

- Section B:

B9: "If the task is too difficult, I get frustrated, but I try to finish it within my capabilities."

- Section F:

F5: "I only do tasks that look very easy. If they are very difficult, I prefer to leave them for later because these types of tasks cause me frustration when I can't solve them."

Physical environment of the classroom

How does the classroom environment (noise, comfort) affect your ability to learn?

- Section A:

A6: "The classroom is comfortable, it's quiet, and I can concentrate well."

- Section B:

B7: "Sometimes there is noise that distracts me, but I try to concentrate."

- Section F:

F5: "The noise and discomfort in the classroom prevent me from concentrating."

Academic load and time

How do you organize your time to manage your academic load?

- Section A:

"I organize my time to complete my homework and study. I make a schedule for the entire year so I have time for homework and recreation."

- Section B:

"Sometimes I have a hard time getting organized, but I try to get the important tasks done."

- Section F:

"I have too many tasks and I don't know how to organize them; I don't get everything done, because sometimes I put things off and I don't have enough time."

Table III presents a summary of the most relevant information from the interviews conducted with the students, determining the most representative factors of academic commitment.

TABLE III
INTERPRETATION OF INTERVIEW RESULTS APPLIED TO STUDENTS

Dimension	Indicator	Section A (High Performance)	Section B (Average Performance)	Section F (Low Performance)	Interpretation
Proactive	Relationship with the teacher: How do you describe your relationship with your teacher? Do you think this has anything to do with your participation in class?	The trust students feel in their teachers and the connection between them tend to encourage participation.	The relationship with the teacher is good, but with little direct interaction.	Students perceive themselves as distant from the teacher, which leads to low participation.	A close relationship with the teacher fosters participation, while poor relationships or distance favor academic engagement.
	Intrinsic motivation: What motivates you when it comes to actively participating in class session activities or trying to find additional information on your own?	Most students say they are motivated by the desire to achieve goals, which encourages them to participate.	Motivation varies depending on the interest in the subject or activity.	Low attention spans depend on external factors, such as the need for rewards to maintain interest.	Intrinsic motivation leads to engagement, whereas the use of external reinforcements does not generate consistent participation.
	Interest in the topic: How important is it to you that the subjects you study are related to your interests or your future professional goals?	The topics covered coincide with their interests, converging in the desire to commit.	There are some topics that interest them, but others are not able to capture their interest.	Interest is a skill that is not utilized through interesting topics, which effectively generates little interest in them.	A predisposition toward the study topics increases student engagement; a lack of connection with one's own interests decreases academic engagement.
	Social support in the classroom: What impact do your classmates have on your interest and participation in academic activities?	Colleagues are always waiting to offer support and channel teamwork.	Social support is intermittent, sometimes there is little support.	Social support is scarce, with little interaction between peers.	A collaborative environment increases academic engagement; a lack of interaction leads to isolation, demotivation, and disinterest.
Reactive	Clarity of instructions: How clear do you find the instructions given by the teachers, and how does that affect your ability to complete your work?	The instructions are well explained, and students often ask for clarification if they feel it is necessary.	The instructions are explicit, but some participants choose not to ask any clarifying questions.	The instructions are considered confusing, which causes demotivation among students.	Clarity in instructions leads to task execution, while erroneous instructions lead to anger and refusal to perform tasks.
	Difficulty of tasks: How do you react to a difficult task and what aspects are important for your ability or willingness to work on it?	They face difficult tasks with effort, asking for help when they need it.	Frustration occurs with more difficult tasks, but some participants try to solve them.	Difficult tasks they experience tend to be abandoned or performed superficially.	A positive attitude toward difficulties contributes to better learning, while uncontrolled frustration leads to giving up on tasks.

	<p>Physical environment of the classroom: How does the classroom environment (noise, lighting, comfort, etc.) influence your ability to pay attention in class?</p>	<p>The classroom atmosphere seems comfortable and conducive to learning; they manage their study time appropriately, combining tasks with others.</p>	<p>The atmosphere is rated as negative, with some minor distractions.</p>	<p>The classroom atmosphere is declared uncomfortable and unmotivating.</p>	<p>A suitable physical environment promotes concentration and engagement, while a negative one negatively affects academic performance.</p>
	<p>Academic load and time: How do you organize the amount of tasks you have to tackle, and how does this affect your willingness to complete academic activities?</p>	<p>They manage their academic time well, combining tasks with other obligations.</p>	<p>They have difficulty managing their academic workload.</p>	<p>They have great difficulty managing their academic load.</p>	<p>Good time management improves engagement and performance, while poor management leads to stress and low productivity.</p>

The scheme presented in Figure 2 visually organizes the factors that influence academic engagement, highlighting their relationship with key elements such as intrinsic motivation, interest in topics, and social support in the classroom.

Fig 2. Factors that impact academic engagement

The structured observation guide allowed the analysis of the determining factors of the academic commitment of technical education students, as it allows recording the ideal dynamics of participation in class, interaction with the teacher or response to the tasks assigned to them. The results of this guide are displayed in Table IV.

TABLA IV
RESULTS OF THE APPLIED OBSERVATION GUIDE

Dimension	Indicator	Description of Behavior
Proactive	Participation in activities	Little participation in groups, few individual contributions due to the distant relationship with the teacher.
	Classroom Initiative	Sometimes there is little initiative to ask questions due to low motivation.
	Use of materials and resources	Basic use of materials without exploring additional resources in some cases, but in others the use of materials is satisfactory.
Reactive	Following instructions	Complex instructions are difficult to follow, but those that are understandable are followed.
	Emotional response to difficulties	Frustration in complex activities, showing abandonment in some cases.
	Attention in class	Distraction in some cases due to low interest in the topic and in other cases constant attention.
	Atmosphere	Noise in the classroom that affects concentration

According to the results obtained in the observation guide, aspects that limit the academic commitment of technical education students were identified based on the 3 sections analyzed, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Outline of aspects that limit academic commitment

To improve academic engagement among technical students, it is crucial to develop pedagogical strategies that address the factors identified in the analysis. In this regard, some of the most effective strategies are project-based learning, which improves students' practical application of learned concepts while reinforcing their interest and intrinsic motivation. Furthermore, active methodologies such as gamification and collaborative work, as well as class participation, foster greater engagement and a sense of belonging within the classroom. Likewise, clarifying instructions and creating tasks tailored to students' levels aids their understanding and reduces frustration, particularly among low-performing students. Furthermore, the relationship between teachers and students must be improved by creating an environment of trust that fosters communication and interaction. These strategies,

when pursued holistically, will improve the quality of learning, result in higher student retention, and improve academic performance in vocational education.

IV. Discussion

This study has made it possible to define the proactive and reactive nature of academic engagement among technical education students, establish differences based on academic performance, and develop pedagogical proposals aimed at strengthening this engagement. From this perspective, the results obtained meet the stated objectives and offer relevant data on the need to adapt teaching strategies to the characteristics of each student group.

In the area of proactivity, it was determined that undergraduate students with the highest academic performance showed greater class participation, interaction with the professor, and self-directed learning. Their level of engagement was deeply related to intrinsic motivation, interest in the topics covered, and social support in the classroom. This corroborates the assertion by Reeve et al. [16] that proactive classroom behaviors are positively associated with a student's self-efficacy and active engagement in the learning process. On the other hand, less skilled students revealed lower levels of active participation and greater dependence on external factors, such as having an immediate incentive or pressure from the teacher, indicating a lack of autonomous control over their own learning.

Regarding the reactive dimension, it was identified that the clarity of instructions, the degree of difficulty of tasks, and the physical environment of the classroom all influence students' ability to actively participate in academic activities. In this case, low-performing students tended to perceive instructions as vague and to avoid, as much as possible, tasks that presented challenges, resulting in passive learning. In contrast, high-performing students stated that clear instructions and an orderly and structured classroom environment helped them complete their schoolwork. These results have been found in previous research that emphasizes the role of the educational environment and teacher-student interaction in the development of academic engagement [11], [7].

When these results are compared with other studies, the teacher-student relationship continues to be one of the most important factors that explains students' motivation and academic commitment.[4]The level of attention students perceive from teachers increases their belonging and interest in active participation. The study also supports what Ryan and Deci [19] they described the importance of intrinsic motivation for retention and academic achievement. However, it can also be seen that, within the results, the technical education context requires more pragmatism, which forces students to accept greater commitments to learning.

From an interpretive perspective, the results suggest that technical education should develop distinct pedagogical strategies for each group of learners. Gamification and project-based learning emerge as viable alternatives for increasing motivation and participation, particularly among low-performing students. There is a growing body of literature on techniques and academic engagement that reports that these methodologies are effective in fostering self-directed learning and interest [22], [20].

This study is relevant to teacher performance and curricular design for technical education. It is suggested that educational institutions focus their efforts on training teachers in adaptive teaching strategies that promote active and personalized interaction with students.

This research provides an analytical framework that can be replicated in other technical institutions, highlighting the importance of active and collaborative methodologies, such as gamification and project-based learning, to foster strong academic engagement. In this context, future research aims to combine this type of research into a longitudinal approach that will allow us to understand how academic engagement varies over time among technical education students. Similarly, we propose measuring the effect of certain creative pedagogical interventions aimed at improving academic performance and reducing the dropout rate in these programs.

V. Conclusions

The analysis made it possible to characterize the proactive and reactive categories of academic engagement in technical education students. It was found that proactive behaviors, such as intrinsic motivation, close relationships with teachers, and interest in the subject matter, are more common in students with high academic performance. In contrast, in students with low performance, reactive attitudes were evident, marked by lack of motivation, difficulty following instructions, and limited

interaction with the school environment. This means that the type of engagement and the level of academic performance are associated.

Differences in academic engagement were identified according to students' performance levels. While high-achieving students demonstrated stable commitment, adequate time management, and a willingness to face academic challenges, low-achieving students reported frustration with difficult assignments, disorganization, and lack of interest in the content, due to environmental factors such as the physical classroom environment or unclear instructions. Thus, the above demonstrates that academic engagement is also influenced by the school and pedagogical context.

Based on the identified factors, pedagogical strategies were proposed to foster academic engagement, especially among low-performing students. Among the most relevant are the use of active methodologies such as project-based learning, gamification, and collaborative work, as well as improving teacher-student communication and adapting the physical classroom environment. These strategies seek to strengthen students' motivation, participation, and sense of belonging, thus contributing to improving their educational experience and preventing dropouts.

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